

DURABILITY AND STRUCTURAL EVALUATION OF BRIDGE GIRDERS PRESTRESSED WITH GFRP TIES AFTER 41 YEARS OF MAINTENANCE

Oleg Kornev, Moscow State University of Civil Engineering (National Research University), Russian Federation, kornev-o@live.ru

Vladimir Kakusha, Moscow State University of Civil Engineering (National Research University), Russian Federation, kakushava@gmail.com

Yuri Zhidkov, Moscow State University of Civil Engineering (National Research University), Russian Federation, zhidkovyua@gmail.com

Andrey Lapshinov, Moscow State University of Civil Engineering (National Research University), Russian Federation, La686@yandex.ru

Evgeni Mikhaldykin, YUMATEX JSC, Russian Federation, emikhaldykin@mail.ru

ABSTRACT

The article presents the results of examination of bearing steel and steel reinforced composite structures of a motorway bridge, built in Russia (USSR) in 1981. This structure is the oldest maintaining structure with FRP prestressed materials in the world. Prestressed GFRP (glass fiber reinforced polymer) bars as strands were used to strengthen steel bridge structures. It is shown that the compressive strength and the tensile modulus of GFRP rebars, used as prestressed strands of steel concrete composite spans, remain unchanged after 42 years of the bridge operation. The GFRP bending strength is down by 26.4% due to higher brittleness of the polymer matrix. If the operating conditions remain unchanged, the durability of such structures can exceed 50 years.

KEYWORDS: assessment; durability; GFRP; strands; motorway bridge; prestressing.

INTRODUCTION

The main reason for an early loss of the bearing capacity and a reduction in the durability of reinforced concrete structures (RCS) is corroding metal reinforcement, especially if external aggressive factors affect the structure (Gizdatullin et al, 2016). In the Russian Federation, corrosion protection methods, developed for concrete and reinforced concrete structures, are regulated by Construction Regulations (also known as "CR") 28.13330-2012 and All-Russian State Standard 31384-2008.

Durability is one of the key points in the study of composite materials (Cromwell et al, 2011; Plevkov et al, 2021). That is why much attention is paid to the study of this aspect (El-Gamal et al, 2007; Youssef et al, 2009). A particular importance are the studies of structures with FRP reinforcement after years of operation (Thébeau et al, 2010; Loranger et al, 2017; Esmaeili et al, 2020; Al-Khafaji et al 2021). It is also very important to know the long-term properties of composite materials and issues of aging, which has been studied more than once by various researchers (Weber, 2014; Pavlović et al, 2021; Priscilla et al, 2023).

The durability of concrete and reinforced concrete structures, exposed to corrosive environments, can also be increased by using FRP systems, which demonstrate high strength and chemical resistance to acidic and alkaline environments. FRP strand systems demonstrate high strength (800-3,000 MPa) values and a relatively low tensile modulus (45-160 GPa). Values of density and the coefficient of linear thermal deformation of FRP strand systems are about 4 times lower than those of steel reinforcement bars; PCR is a dielectric, and it has magnetic permeability. PCR performance relies on the chemical origin of the fiber filler and the binder used to make it, their volumetric ratio, the diameter of the reinforcement system, and the production technology. Therefore, the performance of composite

reinforcement systems, made by versatile manufacturers, are totally different. Fiberglass composite reinforcement (GFRP) is a widely spread type of FRP due to its optimal cost-performance ratio.

A BRIEF HISTORY OF THE USE OF FRP REINFORCEMENT IN RUSSIA

Opportunity for effective reinforcement of concrete structures by nonmetallic reinforcement have long been interested engineers and scientists. The idea of using glass fiber for reinforcing concrete structures, first formulated by the Soviet scientist A.K. Burov in 1941 (Burov&Andreevskaya, 1952).

The first demonstration projects with GFRP reinforcement in the world were constructed in USSR. In the 1970s the non-metallic reinforcement was used in the construction of lightweight concrete (cellular concrete et al.), as well as in foundations, piles, electrolytic baths, beams and girders platforms, supporting structures of capacitor banks, mounting plates slopes non-insulation traverses and other structures. Later with the use of GFRP reinforcement were constructed such structures as transverse of ETL's, the top flange of the arch girder in two slip-on warehouses, etc.

The very first design guidelines for FRP materials in the world appeared in USSR in 1978 (Niizhb, 1978). Those guidelines were applicable only to 6 mm diameter GFRP reinforcement based on the research data at that time. In 1980 was published a book by soviet researcher Frolov N.P. about GFRP reinforcement and GFRP-reinforced concrete structures (Frolov, 1980). In 1980-s was an extensive work in the field of implementation FRP reinforcement in RC structures in USSR (Salia&Shagin, 1990). Three demonstration bridges were built in 70-90 years of the last century, under the leadership of Doctor of Technical Sciences Professor Vladimir Kulish with the participation of employees of the Department "Bridges, bases and foundations" Pacific National University (PNU) and maintaining to the present (Kulish, 1993).

- timber-FRP-reinforced concrete 9 m span bridge with laminated wood beams prestressed with fiberglassrods.

- Steel-reinforced concrete 12 m span bridge with metal beams, and prestressed ties with fiberglass reinforcement.

- GFRP-reinforced concrete 15 m span bridge.

In demonstration bridges was used fiberglass rebars diameter 6 mm with a tensile strength 1600 MPa, and the density - 2.02 t/m³. Fiber volume fraction was 80-83%.

In section of Ø6 mm rebars were located 5,2x10 Ø10mm aluminum-boric-silica fibers, and a resin of 20% by weight was enough for its distribution between the glass fibers.

In 1975, was completed the construction of the world's first laminated wooden bridge length of 9 m, with 6 beams cross-section 20x60 cm made of spruce wood and reinforced with four prestressed tendons of four fiberglass rods with a diameter 4 mm (Figure 1). The beams were connected with reinforced concrete slab with concrete strength 30 N/mm².

The second bridge in the USSR with fiberglass reinforcement built in 1981 in Primorsky Krai by r. Shkotovka. The span of the bridge consists of six metal I-beams №45, prestressed with 12 fiberglass rods with a diameter of 6 mm. The study of this bridge is described in this article.

The third span of the bridge - an experimental, full-length 12 m. In its cross-section there is six steel beams united by cast-in-place reinforced concrete slab. As the main beams of span structures were used rolled I-beams №45, and for their bearing capacity was conducted their prestressing with ties of 12 rods fiberglass reinforcement Ø6 mm.

In 2006, on the technical task by NIIZhB named after Gvozdev, employees of the Department "Bridges, bases and foundations" PNU was conducted an inspection of these bridges (Stepanova et al, 2013). Surveys report gave a positive conclusion, with special attention paid to the condition of rebars contact with the base beams.

Careful examination during an inspection of anchors and spaces between the ribs of stoppers filled with an epoxy-cement compound revealed no slippage of GFRP rebars to the main v-shaped bearing structure.

Thus, inspection results indicate the saving of an prestressing effect in the structures of the bridge and allow to claim that the proposed design and implement a technology to anchors, fixation rods in the anchor devices on the beams, received a positive assessment after 15-21 year-old maintenance.

In the Russian Federation now, the use of GFRP bars in reinforced concrete structures is regulated by the applicable building regulations, including Construction Regulations 63.13330.2018, Construction Regulations 295.1325800.2017, Construction Regulations 405.1325800.2018, Construction Regulations 435.1325800.2018, and other regulatory documents. Properties of concrete structures reinforced with FRP are considered in (Lapshinov 2017; Kakusha et al, 2018). The Russian experience of the industrial application of GFRP in the construction of a motorway bridge is addressed in (Salia&Shagin, 1990). The task of this research was to examine the motorway bridge after 41 years of its operation and to identify the principal physical and mechanical characteristics of FRP, used in the course of its construction, to prognosticate the durability of building structures reinforced by GFRP.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODS

The facility to be examined is a composite six-span motorway bridge across the Tigrovaya River; its total length is 48.8 m, and its roadway width is 8.1 m. The bridge is located at the kilometer marker 35 on the Shkotovo-Partizansk motorway in Primorsky Krai (figure 1). Four reinforced concrete bridge spans were built according to the standard project series 3.503-29, while composite spans were made according to an experimental design. The bridge was put into operation in 1981.

Figure 1: The external appearance of the motorway bridge over the Tigrovaya River

Bearing structures of the composite bridge span are made of six I-beams № 45 with the flange width of 175 mm, connected by inclined ties made of 40x40 mm angles and a monolithic reinforced concrete deck slab that is 150 mm thick. Metal beams are mounted directly on caps of rubber-metal bridge piers. To increase the bearing capacity of a span, bottom flanges of metal I-beams were reinforced by prestressed horizontal multistrand anchor systems, consisting of 12 GFRP strands; each strand has a diameter of 6 mm. Each I-beam of the span has a multistrand system in steel casing. The multistrand system is made by means of jacking anchored composite strands. The fiberglass strand system was anchored using anchorage cones and the epoxy-cement compound that filled spaces between the strands. The length of the anchor protection cap was 37 cm; its diameter was 15 cm, and the diameter of anchors of the multistrand system was 11 cm. The design stress value was 69 MPa (0,33 Ry) in the bottom flanges of an I-beam and 634 MPa (0,42 $\sigma_{\text{temporary}}$) in one GFRP strand, having the diameter of 6 mm. The multistrand system, made of reinforcing fiberglass strands, was protected from mechanical damage by metal sheaths, made of 10x10 angle or channel №14, welded to the bottom flanges of an I-

beam. The unprotected part of the fiberglass reinforcement system, that had no metal sheaths, was painted black to safeguard it from UV radiation. GFRP was prestressed by pulling out 117 mm of loose ends of strands using hydraulic jacks. Prestressed metal I-beams were manufactured in a laboratory environment at Khabarovsk Institute of Technology in 1980, and finished beam products were delivered to the motorway bridge construction site.

The pretension force of the multistrand system, that had 12 strands, was 215 kN or 17,92 kN per $\phi 6$ GFRP strand with a diameter of 6 mm. The multistrand system axis was located at a distance of 80 mm from the bottom flange of the I-beam, and in the bridge span this distance was 50 mm due to the applicable GFRP protection requirements. The axis of the fiberglass reinforcement multistrand system could be relocated using clamps made of metal angle №50. Polyurethane gaskets were placed between the angle and the reinforcement to prevent the collapse of GFRP.

The motorway bridge was examined in 2021-2022 by the specialists of Moscow State University of Civil Engineering (National Research University) pursuant to the provisions of National Standard of Russia in the area of inspection of buildings and structures. Broken GFRP specimens, that were up to 200 mm long, were sampled from the areas unprotected by the metal sheath to identify the physical and mechanical characteristics of the composite reinforcement system. These specimens were tested using universal testing machines Instron 3382 and Instron 1000HDX pursuant to All-Russian State Standard 32492-2015. Relative deformations, triggered by the axial tension of GFRP, were recorded by displacement transducers Instron 2630-105. The surface structure of the cross-sections of GFRP specimens was studied at different structural levels using high resolution scanning electron microscope QAUNTA 250 FEG. Reinforcement specimens, that were 8-10 mm long, were cut off GFRP fragments to study their surface structure. Then the cross-section of GFRP specimens was consecutively polished by the sandpaper featuring descending grades of coarseness, starting from P240, P600, P1200 and P2000 and ending with P2500 to bring the surface of the specimens to glossy shine. The SPI-Modele vacuum unit was used to apply a layer of electrically conductive gold that was 5-10 nm thick to the pre-prepared surface of composite reinforcement specimens.

The authors monitored the stress-strain state of the span structures, made of I-beam № 45 and reinforced with GFRP strands, to establish correspondence between the design and the actual behaviour of the bridge structure and to identify actual multistrand system stresses, triggered by vehicular live loads. Deformations in some strands of multistrand systems and in the tensile flange of the I-beam were measured by strain gauges (TML FLA-5-11 strain gauges using thin films) to identify forces in the span structures, that could be triggered by live loads (automotive vehicles). Strain gauges were glued to some strands in GFRP systems and tensile flanges of I-beams at points where access was provided for installation and connection purposes. The serviceable condition of the fiberglass composite reinforcement system was not disturbed by the installation of the strain gauges. Polymer coating was applied to the strain gauges to protect them from moisture and wind during the measurement process. After the strain gauges had been connected to the measurement unit, the measurement bridge was balanced to set the readings to zero (in absence of traffic on the bridge). Measurements were taken for 20-30 minutes; types and numbers of vehicles were registered until the necessary amount of experimental data was accumulated.

RESULTS

In the past, the motorway bridge in Primorsky Krai was examined in 2006 and 2021, or after 25 and 41 years of operation since construction. When the bridge was examined in 2006, the condition of the road pavement, reinforced concrete slabs and I-beams was found to be satisfactory. No GFRP failure or slip was detected, and the space between the strands was filled with epoxy-cement compound. In 2021, critical defects in the bearing structures of the bridge were recorded, and the structures of the bridge piers were considered to be in the emergency condition. A more thorough examination of the motorway bridge was performed in April 2022 by the employees of NRU MGSU. At the time of the examination, the service life of the motorway bridge structures was 42 years without any overhaul.

As a result of the visual examination of the bridge structure in 2022, the following defects were identified: bottom surfaces of reinforced concrete slabs of the span and the deck evidenced concrete leaching, accompanied by the formation of stalactites, scaling, peeling and destruction of the protective layer of concrete with the exposure of corroded metal reinforcement bars; cracks having openings up to 3.0 mm wide were observed. These defects are typical for 70% of reinforced concrete bridge spans. Water leaks and efflorescence were found on the surface of concrete structures due to the water flow from the roadway. Some metal I-beams of the composite structure PS 3-4 had broken fiberglass reinforcement bundles (figure 2). Fragments of strands, that were up to 200 mm long, were sampled from some steel-reinforced concrete spans of the motorway bridge, featuring broken strands made of GFRP reinforcement in order to study the microstructure and the surface, as well as to determine the actual values of physical and mechanical characteristics of GFRP.

Figure 2: Fragments of I-beams with ruptured and extracted GFRP bars

Results of geodetic surveys show that deflections of reinforced concrete bridge spans, constructed in accordance with standard designs, are 16-31 mm, while deflections of composite spans vary from 9 to 31 mm. Maximum deflections are concentrated in I-beams with torn GFRP bars. It is noteworthy that deflections of composite spans with composite multi-strand systems are much smaller than those of an adjacent span strengthened with metal angles.

Some GFRP strands in the parts of the multi-strand system, that are unprotected from mechanical damage, were subjected to complete or partial failure. The visible evidence of failure of GFRP strands is mainly observed in the area of their contact with the ends of protective metal sheaths made of channel №14 (for three beams) and angles (for other beams). It is impossible to identify the exact number of fully or partially damaged GFRP strands of the multi-strand system, because the evidence of destruction

was also found in the areas fully covered by the protective metal sheath (the damage was visually detected through the gaps between the sheath and the bottom flange of the I-beam). Given the results of the visual examination of the motorway bridge structures, the following damage and defects were identified:

Critical damage means ruptured GFRP elements, collapsed concrete, exposure of metal reinforcement bars, and cracks in horizontal structures above the piers with openings that are up to 3 mm wide. Vertical cracks and ruptures were found in some reinforcement structures (the band);

Extensive damage means potholes, longitudinal and transverse cracks in the multi-layered asphalt-concrete pavement of the roadway with the openings up to 15 mm wide, transverse cracks near expansion joints with the openings up to 20 mm wide, lack of expansion joints and waterproofing. Besides, the asphalt concrete coating of sidewalks is damaged, and metal guard rails do not meet the applicable regulations. There are traces of corroding metal structures of the rail, loosened attachment of rail structures, and damaged concrete of the slabs exposing reinforcement bars which are subjected to surface corrosion. The structure features salt efflorescence accompanied by stalactites on the bottom surface of the concrete slabs; the protective layer of concrete is damaged, reinforcement bars are exposed and subjected to surface corrosion. There are cracks up to 3 mm wide and areas of concrete carbonization.

Insignificant damage includes concrete peeling and the presence of soil on the road surface. The bottom section of the piers has loads of soil, trees, etc.; there is no water runoff on the roadway of the bridge. Hence, in accordance with All-Russian State Standard 59618-2021, the structures of the motorway bridge belong to the so-called 'emergency category', requiring immediate anti-damage actions to be taken.

Results of examination of the composite spans of the motorway bridge, that has 12 GFRP elements, 6 mm diameter each, showed that stresses in the GFRP elements and the I-beam under the live load (without considering the prestressing from the dead weight of structures) depend on the weight of the motor transport on the bridge. Hence, stresses in the GFRP element and the I-beam are maximum when a Volvo road tractor and trailer, having a total mass of up to 25 tons, goes over the bridge; values of stresses reach 11.35 and 31 MPa, respectively. Stress-induced deformations in GFRP and in the bottom strained flange of an I-beam are 0.023 % and 0.016 %, respectively. Stresses, arising due to the self-tensioning of strands, subjected to live load, do not exceed 1.8% of the design value of pre-tensioning. The results of verification calculations show that the reinforcement of the composite span structure, by prestressed GFRP ties with a diameter of 6 mm each, increases the bearing capacity of the bridge by 30%. After the rupture of 10 GFRP bars, the bridge capacity decreases by 8.6%, but exceeds the bearing capacity of structures without reinforcement by 18.8%.

The visual examination of GFRP specimens showed the absence of lamination or destruction on the outer surface and the cross section of GFRP; small spots featuring irregular coil pitch are visualized. The main physical and mechanical characteristics of the GFRP with a diameter of 6 mm before and after its operation as part of the motorway bridge structures during 42 years (specimens were cut off from torn strands of the multistrand system) are presented in table 1, and the cross-sectional microstructure of the composite reinforcement element with a diameter of 6 mm is presented in figures 4 and 5. Figure 4 shows that the reinforcing filler is almost uniformly distributed in the polymer matrix. However, the inner structure of GFRP bars has some damage due to rupture (figure 5).

Figure 3: GFRP bar specimen extracted from bridge structure

Table 1: Physical and mechanical characteristics of GFRP containing epoxy-phenolic compound and fiberglass roving

Characteristics	Values	
	Initial, according to (Salia&Shagin,1990)	42 years later
Binder content, %	17-20	-
Binder cure rate, %	80-86	86-88
Nominal diameter, mm	6±0.15	6.08
Spiral coil pitch, mm	2±0.5	0.96
Density, kg/m ³	2,020	1,990
Strength, MPa in:		
compression	400	405
bending	1,300	957
tension	1,500	613*
cross shear	-	188
Relative elongation in tension, %	2.9	-
Tensile modulus of elasticity, MPa	50,000	50,434

Note: GFRP specimens did not fail due to the slip of reinforcing elements in the sleeve.

Analysis of the data, provided in Table 1, shows that the GFRP density decreased by 1.5% in the course of the long-term operation. Apparently, this phenomenon is caused by the extraction from the polymer matrix of low molecular compounds that did not enter into reactions for the curing of the epoxy-phenolic binder. However, the compressive strength and tensile modulus of the composite fiberglass reinforcement remained at the same level. Probably, the value of the tensile strength of the composite reinforcing elements will also remain in the range of 1,400-1,450 MPa (Figure 6). In our opinion, a substantial reduction (26,4%) in the bending strength of GFRP (from 1,300 to 957 MPa) is caused by an increase in the brittleness of a rigid polymer matrix. It is also worth taking into account the differences in measurement methods more than 40 years ago and now. Therefore, epoxy compounds, containing reactive compounds as modifiers, should be used to produce durable polymer composite reinforcing materials. In this case, the durability of such GFRP and structural units will exceed 50 years. From the figure 4 it also evident that there is good contact between the fibers and the resin and there are no voids.

Figure 4. Photo of the cross-section of the ø6 mm GFRP bar and contains the epoxy-phenolic binder and fiberglass roving

Figure 5: Photo of the cross-section of the $\varnothing 6$ GFRP bar with the epoxy-phenolic binder. The photo features the disintegration of the polymer composite

Figure 6: Tensile tests of GFRP bars extracted from the bridge structure

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn on the basis of (1) the examination of the motorway bridge, whose bearing structures are made of composite spans, strengthened by multistrand systems having 12 $\varnothing 6$ fiberglass strands that are 6 mm in diameter, and (2) the GFRP strength value identified upon 42 years of the bridge structure operation:

1. The 43 years old bridge with GFRP prestressed ties was inspected, which is now considered as the oldest maintaining structure with FRP materials in the world.
2. The compressive strength and the tensile modulus of elasticity of GFRP remain at the same level, while the density of reinforcement strands reduces by 1.5%. A reduction in the bending strength of composite reinforcement strands by 26.4% is due to an increase in the brittleness of the polymer matrix.
3. The durability of prestressed composite fiberglass reinforcement strands in the structures of a motorway bridge will exceed 50 years if normal operating conditions of the bridge are maintained.
4. Further research of the inspected bridge and other structures with GFRP bars built in USSR in the 1970s and 1980s needed for better understanding the durability of FRP materials.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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